

POST-WAR TAX POLICY FOR UKRAINE ON THE WAY TO PRESERVING HUMAN CAPITAL**Sushkova O.**

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Abstract

The article justifies the expediency of using tax tools to support young people as the basis of Ukraine's human capital in the post-war period. It was systematized the materials of the scientific studies of approaches to economic recovery in some countries that had a military conflict. Based on that and taking into account the peculiarities of the Ukrainian situation, the author formulated proposals for application of tax incentives to encourage youth employment and entrepreneurship among them.

Keywords: tax policy, tax incentives, post-war economy, human capital, young people, start-up.

1. Introduction.

Russia's military aggression against Ukraine is causing catastrophic consequences for the population and territory of Ukraine, civil and critical infrastructure is being destroyed, certain territories of Ukraine are being occupied, large-scale population migration is taking place, industrial facilities are being stopped or destroyed, and production processes are being disrupted, etc. Unfortunately, the long-term nature of these events leads to a humanitarian crisis and inflicts a greater and greater blow on the country's economy, which will have larger-scale and long-term negative consequences.

The biggest problem of the war in Ukraine is the "outflow" of young people abroad. This age group is the basis of the human capital of any country, the loss of which in the future will lead to quantitative and qualitative changes in the labour force in the future (violation of natural renewal, generational changes, lack of new ideas, new skills, new approaches), will lead to a shortage of personnel and change age structure of the economically active population of Ukraine. All this will negatively affect the economic capacity of the country and the dynamics of its socioeconomic development. Therefore, one of the urgent issues for Ukraine today is the formation of the foundations of the post-war tax policy for the recovery of Ukraine, which will include tools to encourage young Ukrainians to stay or return to Ukraine.

2. Goals, Objectives and Methodology.

The purpose of the article is to formulate proposals for the post-war tax policy of Ukraine regarding the use of tax incentives, which will be effective in encouraging the young population of Ukraine to find employment or start a new business, as well as which will contribute to the development of the knowledge-based

economy in Ukraine. To achieve this goal, the author of the article analyzed the statistics of the forced migration of the population of Ukraine to European and other countries caused by Russia's military aggression against Ukraine, as well as conducted an analysis of scientific research about the experience of some European countries in stimulating the recovery of their economy after the military conflict and in attracting young or high skilled people. Based on the received conclusions, the author formed the proposals regarding the application of the post-war tax policy incentives to preserve the human capital of Ukraine and stimulate the construction of the knowledge economy.

3. Results.**3.1. General statistics of forced migration of the Ukraine population to European and other countries since February 24, 2022**

According to international observers, one of the largest consequences of Russia's military aggression against Ukraine is a historical mass outflow of people fleeing the conflict. According to OECD data, 7.6 million Ukrainian people crossed the border and more than 5.3 million Ukrainian people had moved to neighbouring countries (The UN Refugee Agency). But every Ukrainian is a part of the human capital of Ukraine, and such an outflow of people may have a strong impact on the dynamics of the socioeconomic development of Ukraine in the future.

Picture 1 shows some statistical information regarding Ukraine's labour force before the war in February 2022. We could see that young people are the basis (this is half of the total labour force – 8.1 million prs up to 40 years old in 17.4 million prs) and driving force for the economic development of the country in the future.

a) participation rate of population in the labour force by age group

b) participation rate of population in the labour force by education level

Figure 1 – Labor force in Ukraine as of the end of 2021

Recourse: formed based on the data of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine (State Statistics Service of Ukraine, 2021)

But unfortunately, as of 16 November 2022, there were over 5.3 million refugees from Ukraine recorded across Europe (UNCHR Operational Data Portal, 2022), and about half of all refugees are children under 18 and about 70% of adults are highly educated people (OECD, European Commission, 2022). According to statistics, the participation rate of children up to 18 years old in all numbers of refugees is 48% in Poland (the Office of foreigners), 50% in Moldova (UNHCR), 42% in Lithuania, 40% in the Czech Republic and Belgium, 37% in Spain, 35-36% in Italy, Portugal, Estonia and Latvia, 32% in France and Greece (OECD, European Commission, 2022). A higher share of Ukrainian refugees are tertiary educated than among other refugee groups: of all adults from Ukrainian refugees who moved to Germany 73% have tertiary education, 19% have upper secondary education and 7% are low-educated; who moved to Spain – 61% have a tertiary diploma, 11% have upper secondary schooling and 25% have a professional qualification while less than 1% without any education (OECD, European Commission, 2022).

Taking this into account, the article presents the results of a collective study of the situation in Ukraine and an attempt to outline some key areas of application of tax instruments to reduce the negative consequences for Ukraine and its society in the post-war period.

3.2. The tax incentives as the post-war tax policy tool

An analysis of a number of publications (Van den Boogaard, V. 2018; Bank Bank, S. A., & Stark, K. J. 2008; Mendelson-Forman and Marshatt 2007; Gupta et al. 2005; etc.) devoted to the study of the effectiveness of the use of certain state policy tools to stabilize and restore the economic condition of the country after the military conflict demonstrated that even in such crisis situations, the government of a number of countries sometimes went on unpopular or radical measures (reforms) in order to prevent the decline of the country's economy and subsequently (in the post-war period) to create conditions for exiting the crisis, ensuring economic stability and socio-economic growth (Van den Boogaard, V. 2018). Often, the post-conflict moment

has great potential for reforms in the country, such a period is sometimes called the «golden hour» of post-conflict transformation, and is suggested as lasting approximately a year (Mendelson-Forman and Marshatt 2007). That is, such countries used this window of opportunity after the cessation of fighting and carried out reforms that ensured the stabilization of the economy and, in the long term, contributed to the development. One such instrument of influence can be taxes, which have a significant impact on the adoption of the socio-economic behaviour of individuals.

However, certain conclusions in study (Van den Boogaard, V. 2018) devoted to issues of the development of countries in the post-conflict period claim that, for the most part, taxes are not considered a priority lever of state influence in the post-conflict period, which is due to increased attention in such time for humanitarian and social issues, and reluctance to increase the already large financial burden for the country's population. At the same time, the limited resources of tax administrations of countries affected by armed conflicts sound as arguments against the use of tax instruments to regulate socioeconomic processes (Gupta et al. 2005). But at the same time, study (Bank, S. A., & Stark, K. J. 2008) claim that under wartime conditions, it is a good time for sweeping tax reform, but tax levers of influence should be focused on simplifying tax relations or individual mechanisms, achieving clear and highly specialized goals (but not for a separate groups of interests) that correspond to the strategic goals of the country affected by the military conflict. Also, these levers must correspond to socioeconomic realities, be transparent and flexible to ensure the maximum effect of reforms in a short period of time. Another study (Mendelson-Forman and Marshatt 2007) proved that the main priority in government policy regarding the reconstruction economy of the country after military fighting should be for the question of employment generation as a basement of economic development, moreover, priority in stimulating employment should be given to women and young people (children).

According to the author of the article, taxes have a significant potential for regulating socio-economic relations, since they affect a wide range of interests of all economic agents, and therefore, even in crisis situations, such as a military conflict, changes to the tax legislation should be made in the country affected by this conflict to stabilize its economy and create impulses for further socioeconomic development. But it should be noted that under such conditions, these tax impulses must be very carefully weighed, meet the social needs of the country's population and take into account the peculiarities of the national practice of implementing tax policy. Then, against the background of the maximum growth of cohesion and patriotism among the population of Ukraine, which can determine the maximum support for socially oriented tax initiatives, this will ensure the success of such reforms.

3.3. The practice of some European countries in tax incentives for employment (self-employment)

Looking back at the statistical data, the author of the article came to the conclusion of the need to form a

special taxation regime for young people in Ukraine that aimed to the creation of a knowledge-based economy and preserve the human capital of Ukraine as a guarantee of its dynamic economic development after the end of the war. The special taxation regime provides for the establishment of attractive conditions and prospects for the return to Ukraine of young people who were forced to go abroad due to the armed conflict between Ukraine and Russia.

Thus, the study (Ivanov, I. 2019) provides an analysis of various tax incentives that have been used in different countries of the world to retain and attract qualified specialists. The given comparative analysis of the successful practice of countries such as Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, the Republic of Serbia proves that the most common tax incentives for promoting employment of young or highly qualified people are the reduction of Personal Income Tax (PIT), Social Security Contributions and other taxes or fees from personal income depend on the tax system of the State (Table 1).

Table 1
Comparative analysis of tax incentives that have been applied in several countries for attracting to return or stay young or highly-skilled people

Italy	the Republic of Serbia	the Netherlands	Portugal
Tax incentives			
2016 – 50% reduction of taxable employment and self-employment income 2017 – 70% reduction of the employment income taxable.	70% reduction of the employment income taxable. + 70% reduction of the base for social security contributions	up to 30% reduction of the tax base (salary)	reduce income tax rate to 20%, instead 40%
Requirements:			
- not have resided in Italy for 5 years before moving to the country, and remain in Italy for at least 2 years after becoming Italian tax resident.	- not resident for last 24 months before the day of contract signing, or 12 months before the contract signing mainly resided outside for reasons of further education or advanced training,	- to have been living outside of the Netherlands for no less than 16 months before starting to work in the country,	- not have been a tax resident of Portugal for 5 years before moving to the country
- to hold a degree, high qualification, specialization or to perform managing roles and to be employed or perform activities for an Italian resident company or a company related to it.	- to occupy a position for which a specific professional education is required and for which there is a demand that cannot be easily satisfied in the domestic labour market in Serbia. - a full employment contract for an indeterminate period	- to possess specific expertise that is not available or only scarcely available in the Netherlands.	- performing highly qualified activities in the field of science, technology and arts in Portugal
	- the salary of an individual is higher than the three average monthly salaries per employee in Serbia	- the salary is higher than minimum month salary	
	- to be younger than 40 years old.		
Term of tax incentives			
5 years (from getting residence)	5 years (from contract signing)	5 years (from contract beginning)	

Recourse: compiled by the author based on (Ivanov, I. 2019)

As can be seen from the experience of the above-mentioned countries, tax incentives were in the form of tax deductions, provided for a limited period of time (general practice 5 years) and under clearly established conditions. These conditions mainly related to the nationality of the person and the suitability of his qualifications for the position, and sometimes demands were

made regarding the amount of wages and the age group of the employee.

Also, to stimulate entrepreneurial activity in the knowledge-based areas of the economy, the Republic of Serbia used tax incentives such as expenditures deduction in Corporate Income Tax (CIT) or reductions in PIT (Table 2).

Table 2

Tax incentives applied in Serbia for Start-up Employees

	Tax incentives for start-ups	Deduction of costs	
Tax incentives	exemption from paying the calculated and deducted salary tax (+social security contributions) for salary of founders which are employed in the start-up	<i>CIT: deduction of the amount invested in the work related education or specialisation of its current employees:</i> –the actual course cost (course fee), –the costs of course materials such as specialised literature, –daily allowance, if provided by the legal entity, –travel costs, if provided by the legal entity, –accommodation costs, if provided by the legal entity.	<i>CIT: deduction of the sum invested as expenditure</i>
Requirements	The employee-founder has: - to sign an employment contract. - to be registered for compulsory social security insurance. - to own at least 5% of shares or stocks in the start-up.	- the qualifying training or education courses have to be work related, i.e. in the interest of the business activity performed by the legal entity. - money was paid directly to the institution or organisation providing the course. - contract in which the individual commits to working for the investor after completing the course, for at least 2 years.	- to invest in entities that are registered for providing education services.
Limits	monthly salaries up to 150,000 RSD one individual – one start-up	The maximum amount of the costs that the legal entity can deduct in one fiscal year is not capped	up to 5% of investor's total revenue
Term of tax incentives	for 36 months from the incorporation of the start-up		

Recourse: compiled by the author based on (Ivanov, I. 2019)

As can be seen from the table, the conditions for applying tax incentives for PIT are similar to the conditions for promoted employment (Table 1), but for entrepreneurs separately applied limits regarding the amount of income and terms of applying the deduction (3 years). As for the deductions from the CIT, they are mainly related to the costs of training, internships, other professional development of employees, and other educational measures. It should be noted that there were no cost or time restrictions on the application of such deductions.

3.4. Tax incentives to preserve human capital in Ukraine in the post-war period.

Based on the experience of other countries that have gone through military conflicts and restored their economies in the post-war period, and to promote employment and preserve the human capital of Ukraine, we propose to implement a special tax regime in Ukraine, the action of which is aimed at attracting young people to stay or return to Ukraine after the end of the war. This tax regime provides tax incentives for young people who are either employed or carry out entrepreneurial activities.

In the case of employment, we propose to establish tax incentives for the payment of PIT, Single Social

Contribution, and CIT. According to the article's author, tax incentives for employment should be applied precisely in the complex, since tax incentives should affect the interests of employees, but especially the interests of employers, on whose employment decisions depend. Therefore, we should take into account that according to Ukrainian legislation, the tax burden on the labour force is distributed between employees (PIT and military duty are deducted from wages – together 19.5%) and employers (22%; accrued on the employee's salary, paid by the employer). Thus, we proposed to implement a tax holiday regarding the payment of PIT and the Single Social Contribution in this format: the 1st year of the employment contract – payment of 25% of the accrued tax, the 2nd year – 50%, the 3rd year – 75%, the 4th and further years – 100%. Such tax holidays can be obtained by taxpayers under employment contracts who meet the following criteria:

- 1) an employee must be 15-35 years old, highly educated, and has Ukrainian citizenship or had it not more than 10 years ago;
- 2) an employment contract for not less than 5 years;
- 3) employee's qualification corresponds to the main type of activity of employer.

But taking into account that the main object of influence is the interests of employers, as well as the fact that according to the method of calculating CIT by the Tax Code of Ukraine (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2010), the reduction in the payment of Single Social Contribution will increase the tax base for CIT, therefore additionally for employers the proposed tax incentives provide for the possibility of applying tax deductions without limitation for the additional social benefits provided to employees (food, accommodation, health insurance, transport, etc.).

In the case of self-employment, young people will receive tax benefits either for the payment of PIT and the Single Social Contribution or for the payment of the Single Tax and the Single Social Contribution, depending on the taxation system that the entrepreneur chooses. If an entrepreneur chooses the General tax system he could get a tax holiday regarding payment of the Personal Income Tax (regular tax rate is 18%) and the Single Social Contribution (regular tax rate is 22%) according to the following scheme: the 1st year after registration of an entrepreneur or a new start-up – payment of 25% of the accrued tax, the 2nd year – 50%, the 3rd year – 75%, the 4th and further years – 100%. If an entrepreneur chooses the Simplified tax system, for the first 5 years of his activity he could get tax incentives regarding payment of the Single Tax as payment of only 50% of the tax rate for the relevant group of taxpayers (I, II or III group), and also regarding payment of the Single Social Contribution – 70% of the accrued amount. The main requirements for obtaining these tax benefits are:

1) an entrepreneur must be 18-40 years old and has Ukrainian citizenship, or had it not more than 10 years ago;

2) the first registration as an entrepreneur or founding a new start-up.

It should be noted that establishing a condition regarding citizenship will only be possible during the process of obtaining Ukraine the status of an EU member, after obtaining it this condition will be considered a discriminatory rule.

The above tax incentives apply to young people aged 15 to 40. But in order to achieve the set goal (creating a knowledge-based economy and preserving the human capital of Ukraine), it is necessary to also provide tax incentives for school-aged children. Thus, one of the main factors influencing school-aged children's and their parents' decision-making regarding the centre of their life interests is the opportunity to receive quality and affordable education. Therefore the other tax incentive we proposed focuses on private sector involvement in education. These tax incentives will attract the private sector to participate in dual education programs and guarantee students of these programs employment after graduation.

As a promising direction in developing the educational services market in Ukraine is the dual form of education, the paper's author consider that it is necessary to provide additional incentives for enterprises to attract them to participate in such educational programs. Thus, Ukrainian enterprises participating in the dual education system could get the tax incentives as

two types of the tax deduction for CIT (regular tax rate is 18%):

1) a deduction of all types of expenses associated with the education of a future employee;

2) a double deduction from the company's income of the salary of such an employee during the first years of the employment contract duration.

The main requirements for obtaining these tax benefits are:

1) *a signed trilateral agreement between the enterprise, the university, and the student;*

2) *an employment contract for not less than 3 years after graduation.*

It should be noted that at the time of writing this article, the proposed scheme for providing tax holidays is taken as a basis, it is necessary to clarify the expected share (%) of tax payments based on analytical calculations and forecast data of the economic situation in Ukraine. Due to the lack of access to official statistical information on the public finances of Ukraine today, the execution of these calculations is significantly complicated.

4. Conclusions.

Summarizing the obtained conclusions, the author believes that thanks to the use of the window of opportunity in the post-war period and the application of both types of tax incentives, Ukraine will ensure the creation of the most favorable conditions for young people to develop and realize their potential, thereby forming the foundation for the preservation of Ukrainian human capital and the development of the knowledge-based economy in the future.

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